

Annex V

Future Works

Annex to Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars

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The annex *Future Work* is addressing the proposed axis of research and actions identified to yield the largest progress on the question addressed in *Kingmakers life's gateway to the stars*.

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a) Further theoretical work

Computing incertitudes

For an easier handling, incertitude calculations would be interesting to provide along each estimation.

Integrating the effect of dust

Interstellar dust might have a significant impact on the discussion, by reducing the range of massive and non massive transmitters.

Proposing a strong model for the quantity of stellar systems within a given radius

We have been constantly struggling along this work, with the provision of a robust estimate for mass and energy contents at present time within a given radius from the Solar System, increasing up to the event horizon. The identification of a better model, than the one used in our approach, or the creation of one, would be very valuable for powering up the discussion.

This task is not trivial considering the important scale range, and the requirement for estimates at the present time.

Proposing an online accessible model for the maximal impact

The model used has reliable hypotheses (like the amount of stars within the local volume), and weak ones (such as probabilities regarding life). A reasonably easy task to empower readers with the manipulation of the hypothesis could be to provide an online access to where one could set his own evaluation regarding the estimations of probability for ET, ETI, Habitability, reachable speed for spaceships...With about 10 parameters that one could possibly adjust within the existing uncertainties, one could easily power up with numbers his representation of the odds at stake. More, this online access could be an interesting way to generate interest, while collecting feedback on how the general public perceives these hypotheses.

Probabilising the fulfillment of the hypothetical conditions for the gateway

Further Investigation would be valuable to undertake using the graphset-type conditional graph proposed in *Main document II) Argumentation B) Logical path*, leading to the kingmaker position for humans. Should the identified conditions be possibly constrained by probabilities on hypothesis, a probabilistic estimation of the odds of the creation of the gateway could be

provided, which would be interesting to consider. Indeed: risk may be interpreted as a combined function of probability and magnitude.

When considering risk globally, some of the hypotheses may be interestingly linked by probabilistic relations that reduce the overall uncertainty, have mutually cancelling effects, or conversely be catalytic. As an example of the later, the increased odds of survival of our own civilisation, is providing information related to the ones of the survival of a possible technological extrasolar ETI, and to its frequency out there, itself increasing the odds of anybody picking up something causally related to us, while in the meantime increasing the magnitude of overall possible impact on extrasolar ETIs, which would have been considered more frequent. This relation has a terrible consequence: the closer we are to create this gateway to the stars, the higher the argumentative odds of a wide quantity of beings to be impacted.

Answering the question of random seeding (probes) or signaling (signals).

The universe is constantly evolving, with everything moving relatively to each other. Targeting correctly the destination, for signals or probes, is a critical issue. A question regarding our probability of having an impact outside, is whether a given object or signal leaving the Solar System on a random heading and at random or given speed, has an overall high or low probability to be captured by a system (object), or to be visible from a system (Signal). When considering distances beyond our galaxy, the issue of the ongoing expansion and rarefaction of mass, might be critical, with some bearings leading to a null probability of encountering anything. Answering this question would inform us regarding the pertinence of undirected panspermia strategies as viable ways of achieving panbiotic goals, as well as on the odds for our free roaming space junk, like starshot sprites beyond communicating range, to end up contaminating systems, or be picked up by ET. ([Melosh 2003](#))¹ might be relevant to this investigation

Investigating the analogy with nuclear chain reactions.

Intelligent life has some probability to lead to the conceptualisation of demiurgic universal panspermia projects, which, according to the analysis above, have a probability to be realistic. The proposition of an interesting class of life, demiurgic life, is made, which is actively doing its best to seed the universe, conclusively leading to a probability to some life to emerge, amongst

¹ [1] ([Melosh 2003](#)) Exchange of Meteorites (and Life?) Between Stellar Systems

which some, with a probability of demiurgic life, which is a chain reaction between elements located away from each others.

Cosmology uses models where the universe is modeled as a gas; the question is asked whether radioactive gas models could be tuned so as to be representative of the question of the explosive nature of potentially demiurgic life, such as ours, within the universe.

b) Real life

The combination of realism of the considered hypothesis, with the importance of consequences, and the responsibility that unfolds, on humans, and amongst humans, on people who realise the issue, makes it that real life action has to be considered. While more theory, refined estimations, assessment of conditions, might be philosophically valuable, and will whatsoever be interesting to undertake, the most important yield on the considered topic now seem to be: try to address it.

The worst possible relation to time, space and causality

An extreme difficulty any advocacy related to our topic is doomed to encounter is the distance in time and space where the consequences happen. We are deciding in the decades ahead on Earth but the ultimate consequences of this decision lay billions of years ahead, billions of lightyears away. More, whatever the considered causation, 87%² of the possibly impacted environment lay beyond the feedback range: we'll have no possible feedback on most of the consequences of our choices.

The worst possible relation to imagination

Leaving argumentation and here expressing my opinion, I want to share that my perspective is that projections which rely on mechanism which are not exclusively the continuation of the past, are doomed to be called "fake news" or "science fiction", by us humans who are extremely reluctant to challenge our individual representation of the world, which is based on experience. This might be a reason for our extensive difficulties to reason with exponentials, tipping points, and emergent properties. Only when we are into the issue, only when consequences are visible, graspable, is it part of the past, and as such, conceivable.

² de Sitter model, presented in annex IV, calculated volume within feedback horizon.

Bibliography

1. Melosh HJ. Exchange of meteorites (and life?) between stellar systems. *Astrobiology*. 2003;3: 207–215.